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ADVANCEMENT OF TECHNOLOGY IN IDENTIFICATION-BIOMETRICS

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Abstract

Biometrics refers to metrics related to human characteristics and traits. Biometrics identification (or biometric authentication) is used in computer science as a form of identification and access control. It is also used to identify individuals in groups that are under surveillance. Behavioral characteristics are related to the pattern of behavior of person, including but not limited to typing pulse, gait, and voice. Some researchers have coined the term behaviometrics to describe the latter class of biometrics.[2]

Keywords: *Iris Recognition, Finger-Print, Sensors, Hand Geometry, Reducibility.*

Introduction

"Biometrics" is nothing but the "life measurement" but this term is usually associated with the usage of unique physiological characteristics in order to identify an individual. The application, which most of the people associate with biometrics, is the security. However, biometrics identification has ultimately a much broader relevance as the computer interface becomes more natural. Knowing the person with whom we are speaking is an important part of the human interaction and one presumes computers of the future world to have the same abilities.[8]

A number of biometric factors have been developed and are used to authenticate one's identity. The idea is to use the special characteristics of a person in order to identify him/her. By using these special characteristics we mean the using the features such as iris, face, fingerprints, signatures, etc. [1]

The method of identification, that is based on biometric characteristics is favored over traditional passwords and PIN based methods for various reasons such as the following: The person to be identified is required to be physically present at the time of the identification. Identification that are based on biometric techniques hinders the need to remember a password or carry a token. A biometric system is fundamentally a pattern recognition system that makes a personal identification by determining the authenticity of a specific physiological or behavioral characteristic, that is controlled by the user. Biometric technologies can be thus defined as the "automatic methods of identifying or authenticating the identities of a living person based on their physiological or behavioral characteristics".[5]

A biometric system can either be an 'identification' system or a 'verification' system, which are defined as follows:

Identification - One to Many: Biometrics can also be used to determine one's identity even without his/her knowledge. For example, scanning a crowd with a camera and using the face recognition technology, we can determine the matches against a known database system.

Verification - One to One: Biometrics can also be used to verify one's identity. For example, one can grant the physical access to a secure area by the use of finger scans or can grant access to a bank account by using retinal scanning. [2]

Biometric authentication is subjected to the comparison of a registered or enrolled biometric sample against a newly captured biometric sample. This includes a three-step process (Capture, Process, Enroll) which is followed by the Verification or Identification process.[9]

During the Capture process, raw biometric is captured by the sensing device such as a fingerprint scanner, video camera, etc.,. The second phase of this process is to extract the distinguishing features from the raw biometric sample and convert them into a processed biometric identifier record. The Next phase does the process of enrollment. In this phase, the processed sample is stored in some storage medium for the future comparison during some authentication. In many commercial uses, there is a need to store the processed biometric sample. The original biometric sample cannot be reconstructed from these identifiers.[5]

Figure:1

Biometric functionality

There are different aspects of the human physiologies, chemistry or behaviors, that can be used for the purpose of biometrics authentication. The selection of this particular biometric technique for their use in a specific application involves a weighting of several factors. Scientists have identified seven such factors that are to be used when assessing the suitability of any facts for the use in biometric authentication. The Universality means that every person using a particular system should possess its trait. The Uniqueness means that the trait should be sufficiently different for individuals in the population such that they can be distinguished from one another. The Permanence relates to the manner in which a particular trait varies over time. More specifically, a trait with a 'good' permanence will be reasonably invariant over the time with respect to specific matching algorithm. The Measurability relates to the ease of the acquisition or measurement of the trait. In addition, some acquired data should be in a form that permits succeeded processing and extraction of the feature set. The Performance relates to the accuracy of technology used. The Acceptability states how well individuals in the population accept the technology such that they are willing to have the biometric trait captured and assessed. The Circumvention relates to the ease with which a particular trait might be imitated using an artifact or a substitute.[8]

No single biometric will meet all requirements of each possible application.

Figure:2

Multimodal biometric system

Multimodal biometric systems use multiple sensors or biometric to overcome the limitations of the unimodal biometric systems. While the uni-modal biometric systems are limited by the integrity of their identifiers, it is unlikely that several unimodal systems will suffer identical restrictions. Multi-modal biometric systems can obtain the sets of information from the same marker or information from many biometrics. Multi-modal biometric systems shall integrate these unimodal systems sequentially.[9]

Broadly, the information fusion is divided into three major parts, the pre-mapping fusion, the mid-mapping fusion, and the post-mapping fusion or late fusion. In pre-mapping fusion, the information can be combined at the sensor level or the feature level. The Sensor level fusion can be mainly organized in three different classes: (1) single sensor multiple instances, (2) intra class multiple sensors and (3) inter class multiple sensors.

FIGURE:3

Features of Biometrics

A number of biometric characteristics may be understood in the first phase of the processing. However, automated capturing and automated comparison that has previously stored data requires the biometric characteristics satisfying the following features:

- **Universal:** Every person must possess a characteristic/attribute. The attribute must be the one that is universal or lost to accident or disease.
- **Invariance of properties:** These should be constant over a long period of time. These attribute should not subject to the significant differences based on the age either episodic or chronic diseases.
- **Measurability:** The characteristics should be suitable for capturing without any waiting time and must be easy to gather.

Figure:4

- **Singularity:** Each expression of the attribute must be unique to the individual. The characteristics must have sufficient uniqueness in properties to distinguish one person from any other one.

- **Acceptance:** The capturing should be possible in a way that is acceptable to a large percentage of population. Excluded are particularly invasive technologies, i.e. the technologies which require a part of the human body to be taken.
- **Reducibility:** The captured data must be capable of being reduced to a single file which is easy to handle.
- **Reliability and tamper-resistance:** The attribute must be impractical to manipulate. The process must ensure high reliability and also reproducibility.
- **Privacy:** The process should not violate any privacy of the particular person.
- **Comparable:** The process should be able to reduce the factor to a state that makes it digitally comparable to the others.
- **Inimitable:** The attribute must not be reproducible by other means. The less reproducible the attribute is, the more likely it will be authoritative.[4]

FIGURE:5

Capabilities

Therefore, the main capabilities of biometrics are listed as follows:

- **face:** the analysis of the facial characteristics.
- **fingerprint:** the analysis of one's unique fingerprints.
- **hand geometry:** the analysis of the shape of one's hand and the length of fingers.
- **retina:** the analysis of the capillaries and vessels that are located at the back of the eye.
- **iris:** the analysis of the colored ring which surrounds the pupil.
- **signature:** the analysis of the way how a person signs his name.
- **vein:** the analysis of pattern of the veins in the back of the hand and the wrist.
- **voice:** the analysis of the pitch, cadence, tone and frequency of one's voice.[6]

Conclusion

These kind of inventions related to technology can create a new revolution in the present world and can change the future of this world. It is in the hands of the future engineers and the scientists to use them in

a creative manner. Research should be encouraged in the field of Technologies, which can create many miracles in the current Science and Technology.

All of the current developments in technology directs human a step closer to production of these kinds of processors. Although research in these kinds of inventions is in its preliminary stages, the potential of such technology is endless.

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